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LastQuake: From Rapid Information to Global Seismic Risk Reduction

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Short abstract

The EMSC, one of the top global earthquake information centers, has been empirically developing a multichannel rapid information system comprising websites, a Twitter quakebot and a smartphone app for global earthquake eyewitnesses. At the intersection between seismology, citizen science, and digital communication, its aim is twofold: to offer timely, appropriate information in regions where an earthquake is felt and to collect high numbers of eyewitnesses' direct and indirect observations to improve rapid situation awareness. Engagement with eyewitnesses is based on the rapid provision of tremor detection (between few tens of seconds to a couple of minutes) which is derived from the analysis of indirect information, i.e., Internet and social media searches by eyewitnesses eager to find out the cause of the tremor. Eyewitness' behavior is comparable to real-time seismic sensors when using EMSC websites or LastQuake smartphone app. Crowdsourced data is then fed back into the ongoing information product improvement and situation awareness which, in turn, attracts more eyewitnesses through a viral spread. The use of visual communication for felt report collection has proven to be fast and efficient on a global scale with, on average, 50% of felt reports being collected within 10 minutes. The LastQuake app now includes timely geo-targeted safety checks and safety tips to describe behaviors to be encouraged or avoided after violent tremors. We argue that this simple,affordable system, based on Internet technologies and social media, can reduce anxiety by offering timely information to eyewitnesses and possibly contribute to immediate global seismic risk reduction.

Abstract

The European Mediterranean Seismological Centre (EMSC), one of the top global earthquake information centers, has been empirically developing a multichannel rapid information system comprising websites, a Twitter quakebot, and a smartphone app for global earthquake eyewitnesses. At the intersection between seismology, citizen science, and digital communication, its aim is twofold: to offer timely, appropriate information in regions where an earthquake is felt and to collect high numbers of eyewitnesses' direct and indirect observations about the degree of shaking being felt and possible damage incurred. This, in turn, will improve rapid situation awareness and augment data at a relatively low cost. Engagement with eyewitnesses is based on the rapid provision of tremor detection (between few tens of seconds to a couple of minutes from when the earthquake strikes) which is derived from the analysis of indirect information, i.e., digital footprints of Internet and social media searches by eyewitnesses eager to find out the cause of the tremor. This detection generally precedes detection by seismic networks. Eyewitness' behavior is comparable to real-time seismic sensors when using EMSC websites or LastQuake smartphone app. The hit times on our websites and launch times of our app closely follow seismic wave propagation. Crowdsourced data (felt reports, geo-located pictures, and open comments) is then fed back into the ongoing information product improvement and situation awareness which, in turn, attracts more eyewitnesses through a viral spread, thus creating a positive feedback loop. The use of visual communication for felt report collection, where traditional online questionnaires have been replaced by cartoons depicting different degrees of shaking and damage levels, has proven to be fast and efficient on a global scale with, on average, half of the felt reports being collected

within 10 minutes. Following requests by Nepalese users after the devastating 2015 Gorkha, Nepal earthquake, the LastQuake app now includes timely geo-targeted safety checks to inform loved ones that one is safe and safety tips communicated using cartoons to describe behaviors to be encouraged or avoided after violent tremors. We argue that this simple and affordable system, based on standard Internet technologies and social media, can reduce anxiety by offering timely information and services to eyewitnesses and possibly contribute to immediate global seismic risk reduction by complementing well-established long-term strategies built around improving the seismic performance of the existing buildings by raising situation awareness and limiting potentially dangerous behaviors after violent ground shaking.

1. Introduction

Seismic risk reduction strategies aim to minimize death tolls, economic loss, and social disruption due to earthquakes. With structural collapse being responsible for 75% of earthquake fatalities in the world [1], the focal component of such a strategy is, and will remain for the foreseeable future, the building of earthquake-resistant structures and the strengthening of at-risk structures already built. This is especially true in developing countries [2,3] even if its effective application, as is typical of any costly and long-term measure with tangible results emerging only decades after the initial implementation, can be problematic.

We propose to illustrate how social media and standard communication technologies applied to global earthquakes and closely associating eyewitnesses [4,5] can complete this main strategy and associated prevention measures by potentially reducing some of the secondary causes of seismic risk. These secondary causes are numerous, including indirect earthquake-effects such as landslides, tsunamis and, fires as well as accidents, inappropriate behaviors after the shaking and during aftershocks or inadequate disaster response [1]. Even a non-damaging earthquake can create hazardous conditions and sometimes at significant distances. In the evening of April 7, 2014, a M 4.8 earthquake in Ubaye region in the French Alps, led to emergency lines being saturated and being nearly impossible to reach during half an hour in Nice, more than 100 km away and affected by weak to light shaking (G. Martin, personal communication, 2014). Any situation necessitating rapid medical attention (e.g. road accident, heart attack...) and occurring during this period of time could have ended dramatically.

In practice, the work presented in this article can contribute to immediate global seismic risk reduction at little cost by increasing the efficiency of earthquake response through improved situation awareness [6-9] and by limiting inappropriate, and potentially fatal, behaviors immediately after violent shaking and during aftershocks by offering timely information and guidance.

We illustrate the importance of rapid reporting of felt and damaging earthquakes in engaging with eyewitnesses, the role of visual communication for a global crowdsourcing service and timely geo-targeted safety tips. Finally we try to evaluate the potential benefits of our approach in reducing global seismic risk and explore future work.

2. The overall EMSC strategy

The EMSC strategy has been developed empirically, i.e. it relies on experience, observation and exchange with users rather than review of scientific literature, and exploits standard web and smartphone technologies. It comprises elements of citizen seismology [10] notably its engagement strategy and crowdsourcing approaches, observational seismology and digital communication. It is described in this article in order to offer a framework for understanding the developments that have been carried out over more than a decade [4,10,11]. We also detail interactions with eyewitnesses, data and information flows and the positive feedback loop which enables ongoing product improvement as well as an ever-increasing user base (Figure 1). The information system comprising websites, a Twitter quakebot called LastQuake, and an eponym smartphone app is at the interface between eyewitnesses looking for information and the EMSC [10]. This information system collects data from eyewitnesses and provides them with

timely information. Data collected from eyewitnesses are curated and collated with traditional seismic data to expand and continuously improve our information products [12]. In practice, an earthquake can be the subject of several tens of automatic tweets published by the quakebot and as many updates on the websites. These tweets and website updates include the crowdsourced detections described in the next paragraph, earthquake parameters (magnitude, location) and their updates, epicentral plot, maps, and their updates derived from the felt reports, historical seismicity, links to the user comments and any related tsunami information. Bossu, et al. [12] illustrate the way it worked during the destructive 2015 earthquake in Nepal. In order to limit bandwidth use in the immediate aftermath of an earthquake, the data transmitted to the app is more selective than on the websites. It includes crowdsourced detections, earthquake parameters (magnitude, distance to the main cities), comments and pictures (after validation) shared by eyewitnesses, and epicentral and felt report maps.

Improved timely earthquake information attracts more eyewitnesses and increases the volume of collected data which, in turn, improves product quality, generating a fast and positive feedback loop (Figure 1). There are two types of collected data from eyewitnesses: crowdsourced data (felt reports, comments, and geo-located pictures and videos which are voluntarily shared by users. See section 4) and the users' digital footprint when using EMSC websites, app, and Twitter posts. The digital footprint reflects eyewitness reactions as they experience ground tremors and is exploited in the rapid detection of felt earthquakes, without using any seismic data [4,11,13,14]. Earthquake detections based on the analysis of eyewitnesses' digital footprints are called "crowdsourced detections".

3. Why felt earthquakes are key for public information and how to identify them

3.1 It is all about felt earthquakes

Rapid public earthquake information is all about earthquakes that are felt by the general public (as opposed to detected by specialist equipment), regardless of the former's magnitude. The ones which are only detected by seismic monitoring networks are valuable for seismological studies and seismic hazard assessments but they hold no direct interest to the public, the media or the authorities - except in very specific circumstances [13]. Magnitude on its own is not a robust proxy for predicting the public's desire for instant information. Rather, it is the number of people who feel the shaking which is the more crucial parameter. A low magnitude earthquake occurring just beneath a city may be felt by a relatively large number of people while a high magnitude one, located at a larger distance, may scarcely be noticed or even felt at all. Identifying which ones are felt or not and how widely from earthquake's parameters (epicentral location, depth, and magnitude) is a delicate matter since ground motions for the same magnitude, and at the same epicentral distance, often exhibit strong variability [15], not to mention the consequences of any uncertainties around the earthquakes' parameters [16]. The way the EMSC distinguishes felt earthquakes to prioritize rapid public information is therefore not based on seismological data. It identifies the immediate public reaction on online tools, moving away from the monitoring of ground motion by station networks and instead, monitoring digital footprints created by the human online reaction to the tremor.

3.2 Crowdsourced Earthquake Detection

Thirty years ago, seismologists would know that an earthquake had been felt when all the phones in their laboratory started ringing: with the delay being equal to exactly the amount of time eyewitnesses needed to locate the phone number. Today online and social media searches have replaced phone calls. Starting in 2004, the EMSC was the first to exploit these behaviors and their associated digital footprints to the end of detecting widely-felt earthquakes. Massive increases of traffic to its website [4,17,18] - one of the main global earthquake information sources - caused by the rapid convergence of eyewitnesses looking for information about the shaking they have just felt [14], are automatically detected [11,13] (Figure 2). Subsequently, one simply needs to identify the geographic origin of these website visitors through their IP (Internet Protocol) address to know where the earthquake was felt, without the need for any seismological data [10]. Two other complementary *crowdsourced earthquake detection* methods are in operation: firstly, Twitter Earthquake Detection (TED), an approach that detects a surge in the number of tweets (i.e., messages published on Twitter) containing the keyword “earthquake” in various languages [20,21] and secondly, the analysis of traffic generated by LastQuake app launches, which works in a similar way to that of website traffic analysis by detecting concomitant app launches (Figure 2). These three methods are fully complementary with 76% of the detected earthquakes being detected by a single approach [22] and have comparable time performances with the vast majority of detections occurring within 15 to 120 seconds of the earthquake and these crowdsourced detections generally preceded seismic location [13]. False detections exist but remain rare and with limited consequence (as explained in section 4.1). They can be caused by Internet indexing robots, or by media and public events [13]. For example, on September 16, 2017 an app traffic surge was detected originating from

Mexico City which later proved to be the consequence of a false alert which was disseminated locally (<https://www.hoyestado.com/2017/09/skyalert-espanta-a-mexicanos-con-sismo-falso/>, last accessed Oct. 2017). The latter had lead people to visit EMSC's website for verification. To complement the three crowdsourced detection methods, an earthquake is also considered as felt when three felt reports are collected. Altogether, there were 2,000 felt earthquakes detected by the EMSC in 2016, i.e. only a fraction of the 50,000 it located in the same period of time. These crowdsourced detections are therefore an efficient filter for highlighting earthquakes which instigate a public need for information among the multitude of seismically located ones.

4. A multicomponent information system for rapid detection and massive crowdsourcing

4.1 Publication of crowdsourced detections

Crowdsourced earthquake detections are automatically published on the different components of our information system [5]: the two websites - a classical one for desktops and one for mobile devices (mobile devices are automatically identified and directed to our mobile website), the LastQuake app, and the eponym publication robot on Twitter as a temporary message, including the geographical region and time of the detection and inviting eyewitnesses to confirm the existence of the shaking (Figure 3). Since, in the vast majority of cases, they precede seismic locations, they are generally the first information publically available for detected earthquakes. The detections are not actively distributed (i.e. through pushed notifications) to limit the dissemination of false detections. They are only visible to people visiting our websites,

reading LastQuake tweets or launching the app as the detections are being published. A push notification is actively sent to app users once the crowdsourced detection has been confirmed by and associated with a seismic detection. Seismic detection times are highly variable. They do not exceed 20 minutes for magnitudes greater than 5 which are recorded at global scale. For smaller magnitude earthquakes, which are generally recorded by local networks alone, this time can be much longer depending on the performances of the seismic networks and whether pre-existing information exchange mechanisms with EMSC are in operation.

4.2 Rapid crowdsourcing of felt reports

The crowdsourced detections are published on our multicomponent information system, not only to inform eyewitnesses but also to initiate the structured collection of felt reports on our websites and smartphone app [23]. The tweets include a link to our website and website visitors are invited to download the LastQuake app leading to it being installed within minutes of the earthquake (Figures 3 and 4; Table 1). During an earthquake sequence when several earthquakes are felt in the same region, the number of app users keeps increasing (Figure 4 as was observed during the 2015 Nepal mainshock-aftershocks sequence) [12]. The rapid repetition of felt earthquakes can lead to exceptional levels of adoption, as in FYR of Macedonia where it peaked at 20,000 active users; that is, 1% of the country's population (Figure 4).

LastQuake Twitter quakebot is essential for engaging with social network users and driving them to visit the website and share their felt experience in a way that enables automatic processing for product generation and updates. Eyewitnesses mainly use mobile devices, and smartphones in particular, to access rapid earthquake information [12] (Figure 4 and Table 1). Felt reports are

collected via a multilingual online macroseismic questionnaire on our traditional website or via 12 cartoons illustrating different shaking levels on our dedicated website for mobile devices and the LastQuake smartphone app [23]. In the first nine months of 2017, 62,000 felt reports were collected in connection with 3,600 earthquakes (Felt reports can be collected for earthquakes which have not been crowdsourced detected). Less than 10% were collected through online questionnaires on the classical website, two-thirds came via the app, the remaining being collected on mobile website. Collection is efficient in the seismically active regions of the globe [23] (Figure 5). It is just as quick, with an average of 30% collected in five minutes and half in 10 minutes, even in less accessible region. For example, 250 felt reports were collected within 10 minutes of an M 5.6 earthquake in Uttarakhand (India), on June 2, 2017.

4.3 A multicomponent information system

Although only a fraction of the local audience reached by the EMSC information systems use the app immediately after a felt earthquake, it is by far the most efficient crowdsourcing tool, both in terms of rapidity and volume (Table 1). Despite this efficiency, and although they are installed rapidly after an earthquake, apps are not sufficient on their own. When an earthquake strikes a region for the first time in a while, the websites are the main sources of testimonials and it is only for subsequent shocks that the app is then widely used [12] (Figure 4). This underlines the importance of the different components and the different role each can play depending on the region. This role may also evolve over time.

4.4 Open comments and geo-located pictures

40% of felt reports are accompanied by a comment published on the websites and app. App users are offered the option to simultaneously share their comment on their own Facebook and/or Twitter account. On the websites, the comments are automatically translated into the language of the visitor's browser. They can be rated +/- on the app. We manually delete offending comments or the ones not related to a felt experience but we cannot read them all in time. We also rely on reports from users and check the ones with significant negative ratings. Inappropriate comments are rare within the first few tens of minutes, when the existence of the earthquake is mainly known by eyewitnesses. Comments reflect subjective experiences of the earthquake and are often used to express emotions (e.g., "it was so scary") and perceptions (e.g., "it lasted 30s and was very strong"). Interestingly, even in the same location and for the same earthquake, the reported duration and emotions can vary quite dramatically. Comments can also provide additional descriptions of the earthquake effects (e.g. "objects fell from the shelves").

Geo-located pictures and videos collected through the websites and app are manually validated before publication on the websites and app. They are checked for possible copyright infringement. They have to be informative, be consistent with the estimated local level of ground motion and respect human dignity [5]. In practice, geo-located pictures and videos are not received from areas affected by severe widespread damage where one can expect communication to be hampered and users, understandably, may have more pressing priorities than taking pictures. Rather these tend to come from regions where damage is localized in a number of clearly defined areas. This pattern was observed during the 2015 Nepal earthquake: no picture was collected from Gorkha, the epicentral region where entire villages had been

flattened [24,25], but 100 pictures were validated and published from Kathmandu City where severe damage was fortunately far more localized. The same pattern was observed on September 19, 2017 in Mexico, where the only collected pictures were from Mexico City, 120 km from epicenter where *only* a few tens of buildings collapsed.

5. Rapid situation awareness

Data are collected not only to cost-effectively augment scientific databases, but also, as presented in this paragraph, to continuously improve public earthquake information and raise situation awareness.

5.1 Eyewitnesses as real time seismic sensors

The felt area is automatically mapped within a couple of minutes of a crowdsourced detection by plotting the location of the LastQuake app launches without the need to wait for the first seismic location (Figure 6). Eyewitnesses act as seismic sensors: they feel the ground shaking and by launching the app (or visiting our websites) report the time and location of their observation. Bossu et al. (2014) [14] demonstrated it by locating the epicenter of the 2011 M 5.8 Virginia earthquake with a 30 km accuracy by simply retro-propagating the hit times of its website visitors observed within the first two minutes. The location accuracy of GPS-enabled smartphones is higher than IP locations as they are typically at city level and allow precise mapping of felt areas even for the smaller magnitude tremors when these do not exceed a few to a few tens of km².

5.2 Reported effects and their dissemination

Felt reports describing the observed effects are automatically curated - notably the ones reporting massive damage are automatically excluded as being far-fetched- and merged in a situation map which is regularly updated on the information system (Figure 7) [23]. After a slight adjustment, determined by comparing with reference datasets, results prove to be as reliable as the ones obtained from more traditional online questionnaires. However, the collection of felt reports through cartoons is faster and the number of collected reports is greater [23]. Felt reports are also statistically analyzed to produce a curve representing the average variations of the shaking level relative to epicentral distance and to estimate the number of people subjected to the different levels (Figure 8).

In parallel, EMSC operates a tool gathering automatic impact assessments of damage caused by ground shaking (rather than secondary effects such as fires, tsunamis, landslides...) [16]. The spatial distribution of ground shaking estimated from magnitude, earthquake location and ground-motions prediction equations is compared to the number of inhabitants (determined from the Landscan database of global population [27]), building stock inventory and related vulnerability. The impact results are calibrated on past destructive earthquakes [16]. On the app, the destructive earthquakes, as defined by the impact assessment tool, appear in red, while felt but non-damaging earthquakes appear in color ranging from green to orange as a function of the number of people who reported it and the maximum degree of shaking reported. Additionally, a tsunami logo appears when tsunami information has been released by an authoritative source, as well as a link to tsunami information resources. Finally, comments

and geo-located pictures and videos are shared on the different components of the system as well as on a unique interactive map on our classical website.

6. Safety check and safety tips for risk reduction

The first devastating earthquake to occur since the launch of LastQuake app in July 2014 was the M 7.8 earthquake which struck Nepal in April 2015. An online survey of LastQuake users from Nepal was conducted six weeks after the mainshock to understand how the users discovered the app and collect suggestions for app improvements. In Nepal, LastQuake did not benefit from media coverage and was discovered through viral spread. The main suggestion from more than 40% of the respondents was to offer timely advice on what to do and actions to avoid after violent shaking [12].

The new version of the app including safety tips as well as a safety check, an SMS function for easily informing family and friends that one is safe after an earthquake, was released in September 2016. Bugs in our monitoring system were corrected in January 2017.

6.1 Safety tips

Safety tips are key behaviors to adopt or avoid after violent shaking irrespective of where the earthquake has occurred. These tips deliberately do not cover the duration of the shaking itself for two reasons. Even if crowdsourced detections are fast, they still occur after the ground shaking itself. There is also a pragmatic issue. The classical “drop, cover, hold on” is valid only

where the buildings are safe and will not collapse during the shaking, which is far from the case universally.

Keeping this in mind, five messages were identified, and conceptualized by a professional cartoonist as a way of achieving cultural neutrality (Figure 9). Alike for felt report collection, visual communication was chosen to avoid language barriers - essential to a service aiming at a global coverage. In order to evaluate clarity and ease of understanding, each cartoon was submitted online to the 5,000 LastQuake users who had left a comment after an earthquake and shared their email over the last 12 months. They were also published on our Facebook and Twitter accounts with the purpose of inviting comments.

766 responses were received from 78 countries. The five cartoons tested were considered easy to understand with rates ranging from 84% to 96%. A few minor changes were implemented following suggestions which may have further improved the cartoons' clarity. We acknowledge that this may not reflect the level of understanding that one can expect from people under stress after having just been violently shaken by an earthquake. Furthermore, 93% of the respondents had already experienced an earthquake and results may be different for novices. Their efficiency in operational conditions is not easy to evaluate. However, no complaints have been received at time of publishing.

6.2 Timely geo-targeted safety notifications

The safety tips are available in the app and may be accessed at any time via the menu. They are presented in a timely geo-targeted manner in cases of strong earthquakes through a dedicated notification. For each earthquake of magnitude 5 or greater, the epicentral distance up to which

shaking was deemed to be violent - defined from its preliminary magnitude and location estimates using empirical laws as the horizontal peak ground acceleration of 0.1g - is calculated and app users who are in this area are identified. This area can be small, for a magnitude 5, it extends up to 14 km from the epicenter, and up to 25 km for a magnitude 6. When the user opens the app through the dedicated safety notification they have received, a visual pop-up appears on the screen of the app, proposing to see the safety tips or use the SMS system to inform their loved ones when safe. A link to the safety check is integrated in the app page of the earthquake which has generated strong motion, regardless of the location of the LastQuake app user.

6.3 Preliminary results of safety notifications

Between January and mid-October 2017, there were 52 global earthquakes of magnitude 5 or more for which there was at least one LastQuake app user in the area of strong shaking. Only seven of them exceeded magnitude 6. There were 1,791 safety notifications sent in total, the number ranging from one to 992, with 30 earthquakes receiving only one or two. This illustrates that, except for large magnitude earthquakes and/or the ones located very close to densely populated area, the number of people affected by violent shaking is relatively limited. For these 52 earthquakes, 104 users sent an SMS through the LastQuake app, sometimes to several of their contacts. During the first 30 minutes following these 52 earthquakes, safety tips were visualized on the app by 315 users, and in the first hour looked at 765 times. These values should be used with caution as they are dominated by earthquakes of magnitude 5 to 6 which did not produce significant damage. The strength of the safety notification is constituted by its capacity to provide the right information to the public at the right time, which can make a

difference at individual level by allowing eyewitnesses to make informed choices and potentially save lives [28]. Their benefit cannot be tangibly measured as it is the inappropriate behaviors and fatal errors that did not occur.

7. Discussion and future works

7.1 The Digital Nervous system of our Planet

Social media and smartphone apps are playing an increasingly important role during disasters [e.g.,29]. They differ from more traditional communication tools by offering public participation and backchannel communication [30]. Their usage is diverse and covers the different phases of the risk cycle ranging from the automatic analysis of social media data during disasters [e.g.,31] to communication with communities during reconstruction after a damaging earthquake [32]. In their analysis of Twitter activity during Hurricane Sandy, Kryvasheyev et al. [33] demonstrated that Twitter activity correlates with damage and that it can aid both impact assessment and response. The strategy presented in this article, and developed by practitioners, also exploits social media and their two-way communication capabilities in earthquake situations – a rapid onset disaster scenario - and more precisely in the immediate aftermath to improve situation awareness and contribute to global seismic risk reduction. Rather than harvesting data on social networks, these are used to direct eyewitnesses to our tools in order to enable structured data collection of their observations related to the earthquake's effects. In terms of citizen science, LastQuake is a contributory project, i.e. a project where the public collects and shares data [34]. Engagement with eyewitnesses is based on their immediate and intensified information-

seeking, a normal response in a disaster [35,36]. The motivation to participate in this type of citizen science initiative is called a protective motivation, i.e. where *people address a personal problem* [37]. Jointly with the use of visual communication which erases language barriers and improves user experience, this engagement strategy delivers an efficient and rapid crowdsourcing approach and a truly global citizen seismology project (Figure 5), where participation does not seem to be impeded by possible cultural factors.

Eyewitnesses act as real time seismic sensors: they react to ground shaking and their use of EMSC online tools and Twitter convey information about the effects of the earthquake. From this perspective, the Internet and social media can be considered the digital nervous system of our planet. Ground shaking is the stimulus generating a “*nervous impulse*” which, when detected, offers information about its cause. The amplitude of the impulse i.e. the proportion of the population visiting EMSC websites as well as the proportion of app being launched after an earthquake exhibit variations as a function of the shaking level [14,38]. When De Longueville et al. [39] explored this metaphor, they proposed *sensations* as being created from the organization of digital data collected from volunteers and foreseen applicability “for crisis management, where up-to-date situational awareness is needed”. For EMSC, the *sensations* comprise felt reports, comments, geo-located pictures shared by eyewitnesses, and seismological data issued from monitoring networks (Figure 1). Eyewitnesses are initially engaged by the provision of rapid crowdsourced detections - generally the first information publically available about the cause of the shaking they have just felt. Once engaged, they share their own observations which are curated, collated and merged with traditional seismic data in continuously improved information products, generating a positive feedback loop (Figure 1).

The whole process is extremely fast: crowdsourced detections occur within tens of seconds of the earthquake (Figure 2) and half of felt reports are collected within 10 minutes. One implication is that there is very little time for human intervention and that the earthquake information, data curation and analyses should be automated as much as possible. In this regard, experience gained with time leads to the regular addition of new automatic tweets. For example, tweets are being developed to report the intensity curve (Figure 8), or the number of people subjected to different level of shaking.

7.2 A multicomponent Information System

The information system interacting with eyewitnesses is a multi-component one whose function evolves with time and space (Figure 3). The LastQuake Twitter quakebot aims at driving eyewitnesses from this microblogging site to our website to collect their observations in a structured manner. When an earthquake strikes for the first time in a while, there are few app users and the websites are essential for broadcasting information and collecting observations. The adoption of the app starts immediately after the first shock and since the app is by far the most efficient and rapid crowdsourcing tool, it means that in a classical mainshock-aftershocks sequence, the situation map derived from felt reports for aftershocks is obtained comparatively quicker than for the mainshock [12]. A new component of the information system has recently been added, a quakebot for the messaging app Telegram, following a remark from one of our users, noting that it was far more popular in his country, Iran, than Twitter. Other additions which could potentially contribute to increased global visibility are not excluded in the future.

7.3 Eyewitnesses' Information for Constraining Earthquake Impact

Except in the rare densely instrumented regions of the world, damage scenarios based on earthquake magnitude and location are intrinsically uncertain, and eyewitnesses' observations can provide valuable constraints [16]. In some cases, even a limited number of observations can make a significant difference. This was the case for the devastating 2015 Nepal earthquake. Rapid impact assessment tools, including the one operated by EMSC, predicted massive damage in the city of Kathmandu, which, fortunately, proved wrong, due to the frequency content of ground motion that was only identified after the earthquake [40,41]. However, within five minutes of the earthquake, significant website traffic originating from the city was observed, excluding the possibility that it had been flattened and indicating that our assessment had been overestimated. This essential information was confirmed by felt reports collected later [12]. Beyond such a specific case, a situation map is systematically derived from felt reports and updated in real time. Felt reports from severely damaged areas are rarely collected leading to what is named the *doughnut effect* where damaged zones are free of felt reports and surrounded by lower intensity reports. A similar pattern is also being observed with app launches [38]. Such a pattern is not a proof of damage on its own, only a strong indication of its likelihood and more work is being conducted to unequivocally and rapidly map the damaged areas. Reaction times also inform us about the levels of fear of the respondents. In the same study it was observed that for strongly-felt but non-damaging shaking levels, the felt report collection was delayed by 10 to 20 minutes compared to lower levels: when eyewitnesses are afraid, reporting an earthquake is not their first priority. In the long run, felt reports also improve the evaluation of earthquake impact by defining regional predictive empirical laws of shaking and damage levels (Figure 9).

Concerning the potentially damaged areas, in order to identify lack of app launches caused by communication network breakdown rather than widespread damage, we plan to investigate notifications: which ones are actually received by the users, which delivery fails, and what can be the cause of this failure (e.g. cell tower malfunction). A more ambitious project aims at harnessing the collective power of diaspora through a web platform to improve rapid mapping of damage. Diaspora seems to be active on LastQuake immediately after an earthquake (Figure 5). They would then be directed to a web platform to submit information collected from their relatives and friends and/or check and validate information submitted by others.

High density of crowdsourced data may also open new type of studies. Due to a large number of felt earthquakes (Figure 4), more than 11 000 felt reports have been collected over a 12 months period from the city of Skopje. Such high density of reports may help to map with high spatial resolution local site effects i.e. local amplification of seismic waves due to surface geology and topographic effects (Bossu et al. 2000) [42]

7.4 Exploiting Comments

. Comments were collected, in the first instance, because there was a demand from eyewitnesses: a demand clearly illustrated by the fact that they accompanied 40% of the felt reports. They are not currently exploited for situational awareness. However, preliminary analyses seem to indicate that the mapping of keywords such as “fear”, “felt”, or “broken glass” could help to visualize any key information the comments contain at a glance. Veer et al. [43] in his study of stories shared online following M 7.1 and M 6.3 earthquakes that hit Canterbury,

New Zealand in September 2010 and February 2011 estimates that being able to share experiences, even when the recipient of the story is unknown, can aid the emotional recovery and help the recipient cope with the ordeal. Comments collection may not today be essential for improved situation awareness but may contribute to a larger adoption of the app through the fulfillment of one of the key eyewitnesses' needs after an earthquake. We plan to test automatic keyword (e.g., "broken", "felt"...) analysis to rapidly identify and map potentially informative comments.

7.5 Safety Notifications for Risk Reduction

The analysis of the first nine months after the safety tips and check were launched indicates that there was not a high uptake at least partly because there was, fortunately, no damaging earthquake during this period in the Euro-Med region where EMSC is best identified. Furthermore, it is not a mass distribution tool but rather a timely geo-targeted service offering essential information to the right person at the right time. Safety checks foster connectedness with loved ones, an important need during a crisis, while using very limited bandwidth, which can be scarce in these situations. Visual safety tips can prevent dangerous behaviors and there is no way to evaluate the possible negative consequences they may have prevented. Furthermore, large damaging earthquakes are systematically followed by aftershocks which impact weakened buildings and can cause additional casualties. Safety tips may contribute to limiting risk associated with aftershocks. Safety tips are not going to change the overall impact of an earthquake but they do have the potential to make a difference to some individuals.

Since more people access earthquake information via websites, safety tips should also be implemented here as well as on our Twitter automatic publication. Bandwidth issues may, however, limit their efficiency. During a bandwidth shortage, it is uncertain whether website users will be able to rapidly download cartoons. Popping up a cartoon which is embedded in the app, and as such already stored on the smartphone, is far less bandwidth-intensive. We are also considering integrating safety tips for tsunamis and are exploring the possibility of linking or embedding existing resources related to first aid tips – always to the end of responding to a user need, although this development seems particularly challenging, especially at global scale [44].

If there is no way to evaluate the impact of safety check and safety tips in terms of risk reduction, the improved rating of the app after use can be taken to be an indication that they have been positively perceived by users with the cumulative average of 4.275 out of 5 stars in November 2016 to 4.481 in October 2017 for Android version (rating values from Google Play Store).

8. Conclusion

This article describes the multi-component information system empirically developed by the EMSC for global earthquake eyewitnesses at the intersection between seismology, citizen science and digital communication, how it engages with eyewitnesses, and its main performances in terms of collection of observations. The system exploits only standard technologies, its originality being to offer an operational system which satisfies -at least some of- the needs of eyewitnesses in the immediate aftermath of an earthquake. It turns out to satisfy recent requirements for crisis related apps: offer information in real-time, offer guidance, share and disseminate information, (other requirements are linked to coordination of collaborative help, a topic not covered by LastQuake) [45].

An important observation is that the LastQuake app on its own, despite the ubiquity of smartphones and its capacity to deliver timely geo-targeted information using very limited bandwidth, is not enough. The information system works by also linking its components together: from Twitter to the websites and from the websites to the app. We do not intend to change user habits but rather aim to fit in naturally with preexisting behavior - notably the intensified information-seeking which tends to appear immediately after the shaking - and meet user needs in order to encourage a more widespread adoption of the app.

Beyond offering timely information and collecting data of scientific value, it can also contribute to global seismic risk reduction by complementing existing prevention policies. It can contribute to risk reduction by improving rapid (within one hour) situation awareness through the collection and integration of different types of data provided by eyewitnesses in order to

effectively deploy available resources during the response phase [9]. The safety tips about the behaviors to adopt or avoid after violent shaking, and which, thanks to the app, are distributed to the right person at the right time, may also prevent human loss at a relatively low cost. Neither rapid situation awareness nor safety tips can prevent building collapse which is by far the main cause of earthquake deaths [1], but they may make a difference to some. In any case, offering timely, actionable information during a crisis is better than any medication in treating public anxiety [46], which is, on its own, a valuable result.

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	5 min	10 min	20 min	30 min
Number of Italian Users	2 778	8 194	16 048	19 625
LastQuake app	661	1 478	1 914	2 131
<i>Mobile Website</i>	1 246	4 248	9 515	11 841
Classical Website	871	2 468	4 619	5 653
Number of Felt Reports	329	554	754	842
LastQuake app	282	442	533	580
<i>Mobile Website</i>	42	71	111	126
Classical Website	5	41	110	136
LastQuake App Installations	26	73	130	255

Table 1: Number of people who checked for earthquake information, reported ground shaking, and installed the LastQuake app, respectively, following the January 18, 2017 M 5.3 earthquake in Italy. Although the number of people launching the LastQuake app is small in comparison to the number of people visiting the mobile website, it is by far the most efficient crowdsourcing tool with approximately 80% of the collected felt reports. Values for Twitter cannot be reported due to poor location information.

FIGURES

Figure 1: Schematic view illustrating how EMSC engages with eyewitnesses to rapidly collect data and offer them timely information. When an earthquake strikes, it is picked-up by, on the one hand, seismic networks which determine the earthquake's location and magnitude (left) and on the other hand, by people who may experience the tremors and turn to internet searches and other online sources for information (social networks, blogs etc) (left). The EMSC information system includes websites, a smartphone app and a Twitter quakebot, all of which act at the interface between the two feedback loops shown. These three channels collect data from eyewitnesses, automatically curate, analyze and collate them, integrating them with seismically derived information. The system then produces publicly accessible and timely

information, which, in turn, attracts more eyewitnesses and, subsequently generates more data. This facilitates the continuous development and improvement of the EMSC products based on ongoing user feedback and observed effectiveness.

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Figure 2: Traffic on EMSC websites and the LastQuake smartphone app over time immediately after the M 3.1 earthquake which struck the city of Ohrid (FYRO Macedonia) July 25th 2017. The data shown relates to the classical website (blue), the website for mobile devices (green,

labeled 'mobile website') and the LastQuake smartphone app (red). New visitors are defined as visitors who showed no prior activity over the previous 30 minutes. The spike on the app traffic at 17:17:30 (top) is the consequence of the notification sent to LastQuake users in an area exceeding the felt area once the magnitude and location of the earthquake had been seismically determined. A close-up (below) shows that users start launching the LastQuake app within around 12 seconds of the earthquake occurrence. The traffic increase was automatically detected in 21 seconds from the app traffic and in 36 seconds from websites traffic. There was no detection of increase of earthquake related publication on Twitter. FYR of Macedonia is the only country where the traffic on mobile website is not prevailing. This activity was recorded after two series of felt earthquakes in 2016 (Figure 4) and 2017 which heightened anxiety in a country wary of a possible re-occurrence of the 1963 earthquake which flattened Skopje the capital city [19] and facilitated high adoption levels of the LastQuake app.

Figure 3: Crowdsourced earthquake detections are automatically published on the different components of the public information system: our websites, the Twitter quakebot @LastQuake and the eponym smartphone app. The tweet contains the word “earthquake” in the local language to increase visibility to searches engines and a link allows eyewitnesses to report their experience on our website. Eyewitnesses visiting our websites are invited to download the app. As of October 2017, the LastQuake Twitter account has 50 000 followers, and there are 260 000 apps in operation around the globe. Websites traffic remains highly dependent on seismic activity. On average, in 2016 the website had 55 000 unique visitors daily.

Figure 4: Evolution of felt reports collected through the classical website (blue), mobile website (green) and smartphone app (red) during the sequence of 15 felt earthquakes which shook the city of Skopje (FYRO Macedonia) from Sept. 11th to Oct. 6th 2016 and the number of LastQuake apps installed (black curve) within 400 km of the first earthquake. For each earthquake, the total number of collected felt reports is indicated in the respective column. Magnitude, day, and time are indicated below. A question mark on Sept 12 at 22:00 UTC indicates an earthquake which was reported by 143 eyewitnesses but which was not picked-up by the national seismological institute, probably due to its being of too small a magnitude to be located. The number of collected felt reports is generally not directly linked to the magnitude of the earthquake but rather it will vary depending on the relative location of the seismic activity to populated areas, as well as to the time of the day. The proportion of felt reports collected through our classical website and its online questionnaire is on average less than 10% which also indicates that on average, 90% of reporting eyewitnesses use a mobile device.

Figure 5: Density by region of the 13.9 million LastQuake app launches from May 2015 to end of December 2017. Users are present at different levels in all seismically-active regions of the globe (except China where access to Google and Apple stores is not granted) with the European-Mediterranean region being well represented. The large density of some regions where seismicity is low appears to be associated with the presence of diaspora from seismically active regions. A large number of launches is often observed originating from the United-Kingdom after strong earthquakes in India, or Nepal. We surmise they reflect information searches by the diaspora for the region of origin.

Figure 6: Locations of LastQuake app launches map felt area in real time. Each dot represents a unique app being launched within 180 seconds of the M 5.6 earthquake (star), at 91km of depth, in Romania on December 27, 2016. The color of the dots illustrates the time lapse from the occurrence of the earthquake. The first launch happened 36 seconds after the earthquake, knowing that the P-wave (the first seismic waves) reached the ground surface in 12.7 seconds and the S-wave (the more energetic wave) did so in 22.2 seconds. There were 931 launches within 180 seconds of the earthquake. The circles represent the front of the P and S seismic waves 60 seconds after the earthquake.

Figure 7: Situation map of the 3,776 unique felt reports collected for the M 5.6 earthquake in Romania in December 2016. 145 were collected within 3 minutes and 1,020 within 10 minutes. A comparison with Figure 6 confirms that app launches are an efficient way to automatically map the felt area within minutes of an earthquake.

Figure 8: Variations in shaking levels with hypocentral distance derived from individual felt reports (dots) for the magnitude 7.1 Puebla earthquake which occurred 120 km from Mexico city on September 19, 2017. The shaking level follows the EMS-98 scale [26]. The procedure for deriving the curve from individual felt reports is described in [23]. The number of people subjected to the different shaking level is derived by crossing the intensity curve with population information.

Figure 9: Safety tips proposed after violent shaking to LastQuake app users. Each tip is presented individually on the phone interface. They can also be accessed at anytime via the app to the end of reducing/preventing seismic risk to affected populations.

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Graphical abstract

*Digital footprint, Felt reports, Geo-located pics, Comments

Schematic view illustrating how EMSC uses eyewitness observations to rapidly collect data and offer timely information to users. When an earthquake strikes, it is picked-up by, on the one hand, seismic networks which determine the earthquake's location and magnitude (left) and on the other hand, by people who may experience the tremors and turn to internet searches and other online sources for information (social networks, blogs etc).

The EMSC information system includes websites, a smartphone application and a twitter quakebot, all of which act at the interface between the two feedback loops shown. These three channels collect data from eyewitnesses, automatically curate, analyse and collate them, integrating them with seismic derived information. The system then produces publicly accessible and timely information, which, in turn, attracts more eyewitnesses and, subsequently generates more data. This facilitates the continuous development and improvement of EMSC's products based on ongoing user feedback and observed effectiveness.